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Over 36 Years of HAB Monitoring for the Aquaculture Industry: the *Plancton Andino* experience

At *Plancton Andino* we study the temporal and spatial distribution of phytoplankton, focusing on HAB species and ecological succession. Our data are used to enhance Early Warning Systems [1] and machine learning models for HAB forecasting using the HAB_f INDEX algorithm in areas of intense salmon and mollusc mariculture. The HAB_f INDEX integrates the water column by summing the ratio of each harmful algal concentration to its critical threshold, weighted by species-specific factors [2].

There is extensive knowledge about HABs, both worldwide [3–4] and locally—especially over the past eight years [5,6]—which we can access almost immediately after digital publication. Many authors assume that HABs are increasing in coastal zones, but an alternative view suggests that we are observing the ocean with greater frequency, leading to inherent bias in historical analysis. Some scientists suggest that intensified monitoring associated with increased aquaculture production may be responsible for the perceived increase in HAB events, and that there is no empirical support for increasing global upward trend. Instead, trends must be considered

regionally and at the species level [7].

During nearly four decades of monitoring, we have observed that some species have expanded geographically, possibly due to climate anomalies. Concurrently, economic impacts have increased due to the intensified use of coastal zones and their resources.

The North Sea is an area where both climate change and de-eutrophication efforts may already be apparent—specifically in phytoplankton communities—through shifts in biogeography, altered species composition, and increased biomass of HAB species [8]. Trainer et al [9] relate extreme HAB events in the Pacific Coastal Ocean, including southern Chile, to climatic anomalies. Zheng et al [10] suggest that human activity and climate change are increasingly affecting marine environments, leading to more HABs in Chinese waters.

From a technological standpoint, *Plancton Andino* has implemented digital image analysis of phytoplankton cells and real-time visualization of oceanographic data. We are moving towards *in-situ* monitoring with automated bio-imaging of plankton cells, with cloud-based archiving and visuali-

Fig. 1. The southern tip of South America encompasses the Chilean fjords and channels. Operationally, we refer to the polygon shown on the map as the Southern Chilean Marine Inlets (A). Satellite image of chl a from 4 January 2021. Credit: NASA (B). Watercolour depiction of patches of *H. akashiwo* and sill waters from a front area of Cholgo fjord and Blanco River on 17 April 2024 (C).

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Fig. 2. Number of phytoplankton samples analysed per year over the past 30 years by Plancton Andino (latest data from 2 May 2025).

zation. This technology, combined with predictive models like **BloomPredictor**—a machine learning model for forecasting the HAB_f Index—makes mitigation decisions more cost-effective and reduces risk. Our fundamental question is whether HABs, parametrized with the HAB_f INDEX algorithm, are increasing in frequency due to oceanographic-environmental shifts and/or plankton monitoring efforts. We are reviewing our database—after quality control and enhancement—to test this hypothesis, while considering specific statistical assumptions.

We have monitored and investigated under the POAS+ programme (Programa Oceanográfico y Ambiental en Salmónidos) in the Southern Chilean

Marine Inlet (SCMIn) between latitudes 41°S to 46°S. Here, we frequently collect live phytoplankton samples from fish farm sites without using fixatives (Fig. 1).

The first author has monitored the local marine phytoplankton since 1984 (Fig. 2). The earliest Phytoplankton Monitoring Program (PMP) report was issued in December 1988, following a severe brown tide caused by *Heterosigma akashiwo* that spring (Fig. 4). The initial dataset was archived in Lotus and Excel files, and since 2007 has been stored on a local server and subsequently on Azure. Figures 2 and 3 present basic data from long-term monitoring in SCMIn. Figure 2 shows the number of phytoplankton

samples from the early 1990s to date, noting that the server service began in 2007. Fig. 3 illustrates the 2016–2024 period, highlighting the number of dates per year with a HAB_f INDEX over 3; the maximum was 56 in 2016, and it dropped below 19 in 2017, 2020, and 2024. The HAB_f INDEX trend declined during this period (Figs. 3, 5). However, phytoplankton composition results show shifts in the interannual patterns of HAB species (Fig. 6), particularly after 2004, when *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa*, which affects salmon gills, was first detected.

Final remarks: When analysing the historical PMP data, several considerations must be taken into account. From 1982 to 2015, the number

Fig. 3. Number of dates per year with a HAB_f INDEX greater than 3. This graph avoids statistical bias, as sampling strategies have remained consistent across years.

Fig. 4. Timeline of key events over a 37-year period related to HABs in the Southern Chilean Marine Ecosystems.

Fig. 5. Maximum annual HABfINDEX in Southern Chilean time series from 2016 to 2025.

Fig. 6. Time series of cell abundances (cell/mL) in southern Chile of *A. catenella* (1996–2025) (A), *P. micans* (1983–2025) (B), *H. akashiwo* (1988–2025) (C), and *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa* (1988–2025) (D).

of samples collected was significantly lower than in the period from 2015 onward. This disparity is primarily due to the 2016 HAB events, which prompted the implementation of a more consistent and frequent sampling strategy. As a result, differences in temporal and spatial sampling effort

introduce an inherent bias in historical comparisons (Fig. 2).

For the 2015–2025 period, we used the HAB_f INDEX to characterize the distribution and risk of HAB events. Since the algorithm includes all harmful species in its calculation, it is particularly useful for general analyses

of HAB dynamics. Overall results from POAS+ (Figs. 3, 5) show no significant increase in the frequency or intensity of the HAB_f INDEX over the past decade. However, the frequency of HAB events varies among species [11]. For example, *A. catenella* was less frequent during the past 10 years, while *P. micans*, *H.*

akashiwo, and *Pseudochattonella* were more frequent during the same period.

HAB events in SCMI are driven by multiple factors. Climate anomalies, for instance, can alter freshwater inflows and lead to oceanographic changes, such as shifts in nutrient stoichiometry [12] in estuaries and fjords, creating favourable niches for certain species. Some photoautotrophic flagellates are better adapted to these changing nutrient ratios (less silicate) and to density gradients. On a broader scale, global phenomena such as El Niño can create environmental conditions that favour HAB development, as observed in 2016, among others.

Looking ahead, our main challenge is to automate the monitoring programme using *in situ* digital and bio-imaging technologies, combining them with predictive numerical models or machine learning algorithms. This approach could enable a more robust and responsive monitoring system—one capable of reducing or mitigating the negative effects of HABs.

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Alejandro Clément, CEO,
Plancton Andino

Authors

Alejandro Clément, Nicole Correa, Stephanie Saez, Francisca Muñoz, Carmen G Brito, Carlos Flores, Laura Latorre-Melín, María J Calderón, Carla Palma, Alvaro Jorquera, Carmen Tellez & Gustavo Contreras. Plancton Andino SpA., Chile. www.plancton.cl

Email corresponding author:
aclement@plancton.cl

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